

Visual FML Editor for data transformations by analysts using TermX

Igor Bossenko^{b,1}, Gunnar Piho^{b,2}, Roman Bondarev^b, Peeter Ross^{a,3}

^a*Department of Health Technologies, TalTech, Tallinn, 19086, Estonia*

^b*Department of Software Science, TalTech, Tallinn, 19086, Estonia*

Abstract

Background: In healthcare informatics, there is a common need for data transformation between various enterprise internal data formats and/or data interoperability standards, such as HL7 V2, HL7 V3 and CDA, and HL7 FHIR, as well as their various versions. Most of these data transformations are hard-coded and written in programming languages that are often inaccessible or unclear to business analysts. Sometimes, data transformations are implemented using transformation languages such as XSLT or FHIR Mapping Language (FML), which are designed for powerful and comprehensive data transformations rather than for user-readability for analysts. This creates a potential obstacle to data transformations' design, validation, and maintenance.

Objective: This paper discusses data transformation using FML and presents an editor for language to facilitate the design and visualisation of the transformations.

Methods: The visual FML Editor was developed based on the FHIR specification, the StructureMap HAPI reference implementation and the TermX interoperability solution. Several FHIR experts have been providing functional and technical input in the design and validation of the FML Editor.

Results: The first part of this paper discusses the platform-agnostic

Email addresses: igor.bossenko@taltech.ee (Igor Bossenko),
gunnar.piho@taltech.ee (Gunnar Piho), peeter.ross@taltech.ee (Peeter Ross)

¹ORCID: 0000-0003-1163-5522

²ORCID: 0000-0003-4488-3389

³ORCID: 0000-0003-1072-7249

and implementation-independent FHIR Mapping Language (FML) designed for data transformation from one data model to another. The second part of the paper delves into creating a visual FML Editor designed specifically for business analysts. The core purpose of the FML editor is to visualise data transformations, hide the complexity of the FML language, and enable analysts to adapt to its usage quickly.

Conclusions: We evaluate the usability of visual FML Editor for transforming a simple logical data model into a single FHIR resource and transforming complex data models into a Bundle of FHIR resources. 100% of participants coped with transforming simple data models after an hour of training, and 75% with transforming complex data models after two hours of training.

Keywords: Data transformation, FML, FHIR Mapping Language, visual FML Editor, mapping designer, TermX
2000 MSC: 68P05, 68Q42

1. Introduction

In everyday reality, it is a common need to translate companies' internally used data formats to information exchange standard formats or outdated versions of these formats to more contemporary ones. These standards could be conceptually distinct, such as the transition between HL7 V3 and HL7 FHIR, or involve different versions of the same standard, like the shift from FHIR R3 to FHIR R4, or even data transformations between different adaptations of the same version because of the using of different terminology or extensions.

Often, software developers have to support many standards at the same time. This situation forces one to choose the preferred standard for storing information and a methodology for converting data from an information storage standard to an information exchange standard and vice versa.

Different standards approach the design of data models with varying philosophies. For example, the HL7 Reference Implementation Model (RIM) used within HL7 V3 aims to encompass the full spectrum of possible healthcare scenarios [1]. In contrast, HL7 FHIR provides a common model, but instead of constraining the scope to attempt to define a global model for all aspects of healthcare, it follows the 80/20 principle, designing its resources to the most common healthcare scenarios while incorporating an

extension mechanism to accommodate attributes that may be absent from the models [2][3]. Other standards and organisations, national or global, may define data models for specific purposes. For example, OMOP defines a Common Data Model for a more limited scope of application [4].

The tasks undertaken by application software vendors often don't align closely with the data models established by existing interoperability standards. This prompts system designers to formulate custom data models tailored to address their application-specific challenges most effectively. In such cases, the requirement to convert data from a local data model into a model or models that adhere to interoperability standards becomes inevitable.

New versions of interoperability standards often introduce modifications to information models. As described by Bossenko [5], these changes can fall into the categories of forward and backward compatibility. To illustrate, envision a scenario where a developer constructs a FHIR-first application [6] based on the FHIR R4 information model; in such a case, data transformation becomes imperative to accommodate the simultaneous support of the FHIR R5 version.

Figure 1 demonstrates differences in the Organization model between FHIR versions R4 and R5. The type of attribute *contact* changed from *BackboneElement*, which means complex elements within a resource to the *ExtendedContactDetail*. In the substructure, the cardinality of *name* changed from 0..1 to 0..*, and two subelements were added. The data conversion from R4 to R5 is possible, but data conversion from R5 to R4 is possible with data loss only.

Even when using the same standard and version, achieving harmony in communication protocols across organisations remains problematic. Organisations may adopt different terminology and extensions, making messages incompatible with each other [7].

2. Problem

Regardless of the specific implementations of the information storage standard, every application software developer is responsible for accommodating multiple standards, their versions and data transformations between them. Such implementations demand significant resources and documenting them becomes challenging. Often, these transformations are

Figure 1: Difference between Organization model in the FHIR R4 and R5.

hard-coded into the source code, making them opaque to business analysts, difficult to reuse, rigid, and difficult to maintain long-term [8].

This paper answers the following questions:

1. What methods exist for transforming data models and structures in healthcare, and which among them are amenable to business analysts?
2. Is it possible to create a graphical interface for describing transformations in the context of a particular language for representing transformations?

3. Solution

3.1. Previous works

In most cases, discussions about data transformation entail the creation of source code to execute the necessary transformations. Below are several potential approaches for generating such source code:

1. JSON/XML DOM-based development: This method uses the Document Object Model (DOM) to programmatically read, manipulate, and modify XML or JSON documents using standard libraries. It typically requires a fully customised implementation for performing transformations.
2. Template-based development: Template-based development integrates templates with data models to generate the desired output. It involves

creating templates with placeholders and using a transformation engine to apply data to these templates. Examples of template engines include FreeMarker, Mustache, and more.

3. Libraries with pre-implemented models: Some companies create libraries that adhere to existing specifications. These libraries contain models, parsers, serialisation tools, and more. For instance, HAPI provides Java libraries for HL7 2.x and FHIR, while Microsoft offers C# libraries tailored for HL7 FHIR.
4. Transformation servers: These servers have access to the data they need to interact with. Examples include Mirth Connect, Iguana Healthcare Integration Engine, and BizTalk. While their primary focus is on reliable message delivery, they also offer extensive capabilities for data transformation aligned with diverse standards. Many of these servers are commercial and platform/language-dependent.

Developers commonly adopt one or a combination of these approaches, augmenting them with various utilities and capabilities to minimise the need for repetitive code. In most cases, writing code remains the most effective method in terms of development time and performance, particularly in the short term. Nevertheless, this method presents certain limitations [8], including 1) inadequate documentation, 2) dependence on the underlying framework and/or programming language and difficulty to reuse, 3) dependency on the developer and difficulty to maintain long-term.

To address these issues, the concept of a “Mapping Language” was conceptualised [9]. The essence of this transformation language lies in establishing a platform-independent specification that can be implemented across various programming languages. It provides a simplified and comprehensible syntax for business analysts and allows the reuse of transformations, such as from HL7 CDA or HL7 V2 to FHIR.

Currently, within the healthcare domain, there is one officially recognised mapping language - FML (FHIR Mapping Language), which we will explore.

3.2. FHIR Mapping Language

The FHIR Mapping Language (FML)[10] is a relatively new, bespoke transformation language specifically designed to transform HL7 FHIR resources to alternative representations, including different FHIR resources,

C/CDE documents, etc[11]. The FHIR Management Group created the mapping language as a specification of the QVT framework[12] for model-transformation languages. QVT is particularly useful in model-driven development (MDD) and model transformation tasks.

Conceptually, FML is similar to XSLT in that it (a) consists of declarative rules that are automatically matched to input data, (b) includes a sub-language (“FHIRPath”) to reference parts of source parse trees, and (c) can reference external functions written in different languages. The source input of FML supports any object models and rendering syntaxes conformant with OMG’s Meta Object Facility (MOF)⁴ language. MOF is a general formalism for representing object models as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs). MOF-compliant models can use various syntactic constructs to represent the classes, attributes, and attribute values of such graphs.

The mapping language describes how one set of directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) is transformed into another set of DAGs[10].

The applications of this language encompass several scenarios:

- Mapping FHIR resources across different versions of FHIR
- Converting sections of HL7 C-CDA documents into multiple FHIR resources
- Translating HL7 V2 messages into multiple FHIR resources
- Adapting any structured data format into another structured data format, including the mapping to multiple FHIR resources

The technical specification of FML [10] has been published as an integral component of the FHIR specification [13]. FML serves as a tool for transforming structured models from one form to another. Within the HL7 FHIR context, FML is utilised to map FHIR resources across different versions of FHIR. FML transformation requires (Figure 2):

- One input model (marked on the picture with the number “1”);
- At least one output model (2);
- Human-readable mapping directives (3) that outline how to transform input into output;

⁴<http://www.omg.org/mof/>

Figure 2: Components of FML transformation.

- Machine-processable StructureMap (4) created as a result of the compilation mapping directive;
- One input instance that corresponds to the input model in JSON or XML format (5);
- Transformation engine (6) that will execute the transformation of the input instance to the output instance (7) based on models and maps.

The source (1) and target (2) models should be described as instances of StructureDefinition resource. The transformation map (3) should be represented as an instance (4) of the StructureMap [14] resource. The StructureMap resource defines a detailed set of rules that outline the relationship between one structure and another and provides sufficient detail to allow for automated instance conversion. The StructureMap is constructed from rules forming an acyclic graph, creating a comprehensive transformation framework. The example of the FML transformation is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Example of FML transformation.

Listing 1 demonstrates the full syntax of the FML transformation in box 3 on Figure 3 from the TLeft resource to the TRight resource. Listing 2 contains the example of an input instance of the type TLeft. Listing 3 contains an output instance of type TRight as a result of transformation.

```

/// url = 'http://example.org/fhir/StructureMap/example1'
/// name = 'example1'
/// title = 'The example of transformation TLeft to TRight'

uses "http://example.org/fhir/StructureDefinition/TLeft" alias
  TLeft as source
uses "http://example.org/fhir/StructureDefinition/TRight" alias
  TRight as target

group main(source src : TLeft, target tgt : TRight) {
  src.a as x -> tgt.b = x "rule1";
}

```

Listing 1: The FML presentation of transformation from TLeft to TRight.

```

{
  "resourceType": "TLeft",
  "a": "TermX"
}

```

Listing 2: The example of input instance of type TLeft.

```

{
  "resourceType": "TRight",
  "b": "TermX"
}

```

Listing 3: The example of output instance of type TRight.

```

"group" : [{
  "name" : "main",
  "input" : [{
    "name" : "src",
    "type" : "TLeft",
    "mode" : "source"
  }],
  "name" : "tgt",
  "type" : "TRight",
  "mode" : "target"
}],
"rule" : [{
  "name" : "rule1",
  "source" : [{
    "context" : "src",
    "element" : "a",
    "variable" : "x"
  }],
  "target" : [{
    "context" : "tgt",
    "element" : "b",
    "transform" : "copy",
    "parameter" : [{
      "valueId" : "x"
    }]
  }]
}]
}

```

Listing 4: Fragment of StructureMap copying from TLeft.a to TRight.b.

```

group main(source src : TLeft, target tgt : TRight) {
  src.a as x -> tgt.b = x "rule1";
}

```

Listing 5: Fragment of FML transformation copying from model TLeft.a to TRight.b.

Unfortunately, the structured layout of the StructureMap (DAG) is not inherently human-readable. Even a simple operation, such as copying an attribute from an input object to an output object, requires the format depicted in Listing 4. A functional language FML (FHIR Mapping Language) was developed to improve readability. An analogous construction for attribute copying in functional notation appears as illustrated in Listing 5.

Listing 5 encompasses the declaration of a transformation group "main" with the definitions of the source structure TLeft, and the target structure TRight. The variables **src** and **tgt** denote the source and target objects, respectively. The rule on the first line incorporates two directives. The segment preceding the arrow *src.a as x* signifies "assign the value of attribute **a** from object **src** to variable **x**". Conversely, the segment after the arrow, *tgt.b = x*, signifies the directive to "assign the value of the variable **x** to the attribute **b** of the target object **tgt**". Each rule must have a distinct name; in this instance, it is identified as **rule1**.

Every transformation engine that supports the FML syntax must provide a "compile" method for translating the functional representation into the corresponding StructureMap. The list of FML features includes:

- Declaration of metadata
- References to structure definitions along with mode specification
- Map imports
- Declarations of constants
- Nested group declarations
- Definitions of transformation rules
 - Usage of variables
 - Utilisation of "where" and "check" conditions
 - Iteration through arrays
 - Integration of transformation functions
 - Type manipulation and casting
 - Dependent rule definitions
- Both the Mapping Language and the StructureMap resource are built upon the foundation of FHIRPath [15], and the functionalities of FHIRPath can be used for transformations.

Due to the complexity and detailed nature of the mappings, editing FML mappings is painstaking work that is prone to minor errors that take time to validate, given the ecosystem design. Typically, the author creates the map,

then compiles it in another system, and then uses the same or yet another system to run some transformations to see if they meet their purpose. Editing a simple map usually takes hours, including validation, which requires specific tooling.

3.3. FML implementations

The following code libraries serve as implementations of the FHIR Mapping Language [16] specification and offer transformation engines:

- Java: HAPI FHIR StructureMap implementation [17]
- C#: A direct port of the Java implementation to .Net [18]

As a result of utilising the HAPI FHIR library, it was ascertained that it only partially implements the FML specification. Notably, the HAPI FHIR library does not support several key aspects, including:

- Multiple input sources
- Functions like dateOp, pointer, escape, id, qty, contactPoint
- Implicit type parameter casting

For example, lacking support for multiple input sources makes the source code more complex. The Listing 6 shows a source code snippet for string concatenation that complies with the FML specification but is not supported by HAPI FHIR.

```
group example(source src : SourcePatient, target tgt : TargetPatient) {
  src.firstName as fn, src.lastName as ln ->
  tgt.fullName = append(fn, ln) "multiple-sources-not-supported-by-hapi";
}
```

Listing 6: Fragment of unsupported FML transformation

One of the most noteworthy implementations revolves around converting data from HL7 CDA to HL7 FHIR within the Austrian Electronic Health Record System ELGA [19]. To facilitate this conversion process, a consolidated library of CDA templates [20][21] was developed in the form of StructureDefinition [22].

3.4. Method

The main goal of this project was to create a tool for business analysts that allows for the transformation of informational models, leverages FML language, and hides the complexity of the FML language.

We excluded software such as BizTalk and Iguana because of the commercial licenses and the lack of FML support. We excluded Mirth Connect due to the lack of FML support, the need to code in Javascript, and the huge infrastructure included with the server that is not needed for our task.

We preferred FHIR Mapping Language and HAPI FHIR implementation because of 1) the official support of HL7, 2) the successful implementation of the large-scale national project ELGA, 3) the native support of the FHIR standard, and 4) the availability of open-source implementation.

Due to the lack of visual FML editors, we will create our own visual FML editor. The results will be validated through two assessments involving people with no previous FML experience: one after 2 hours and the other after 4 hours of training.

4. Results

4.1. TermX

A TermX [23] FML module was created as part of this work. This module facilitates the creation of FML transformations, which can be done through a user-friendly visual FML editor. It also enables data transformation using FML transformations. TermX is an open-source interoperability suite with terminology management, knowledge sharing, modelling, authoring and publishing modules. This work aimed to create a visual editor to conceal the complexity of the FML language and facilitate rapid adaptation to it. It was planned to reach the TRL 6 level by the European Commission Technology Readiness Level classification [24].

The visual FML editor is the main contribution of this article.

4.2. Development process

The process was divided into 3 phases - analysis, development and verification. The analysis phase included work on FHIR FML specification,

Figure 4: TermX sandbox for management of FML transformation.

analysis of available examples⁵⁶, analysis of the source code of ELGA project⁷ and meetings with FHIR experts in the field of FML, which included Jose Costa Teixeira⁸, Vadim Peretokin⁹ and Oliver Egger¹⁰. As a result of the analysis, a specification and mock-up were created for the environment for management of FML transformations (sandbox) and editor.

The development phase began with the creation of a sandbox. Sandbox 4 that allows you to load definitions of structures, concept maps and other transformations from different sources. Sandbox also allows you to preview data structures, generate the initial boilerplate source code for the

⁵<https://github.com/ahdis/fhir-mapping-tutorial>
⁶<https://fhirpath-lab.azurewebsites.net/FhirMapper2>
⁷<https://github.com/hl7ch/cda-fhir-maps>
⁸<https://www.linkedin.com/in/costateixeira>
⁹<https://www.linkedin.com/in/vadimperetokin>
¹⁰<https://www.linkedin.com/in/oliveregger>

Figure 5: Example of the simplest visual transformation from TLeft.a to TRight.b.

transformation, compile the transformation, generate an input instance for the transformation, and execute the transformation. Sandbox allows you to save created transformations and instances and export them to FML and FHIR StructureMap standards. During the implementation process, the open-source code of the Matchbox server¹¹ was analyzed. However, since Matchbox was based on the HAPI FHIR libraries, it was decided to use only the HAPI FHIR implementation to work with FHIR StructureMap and transform instances. Projects found in the analysis phase were transferred to the sandbox to check its functionality. After this, the development of a visual editor for transformations began. Validation stage. Starting from the third month of development, an external expert, Jose Costa Teixeira, was brought in. Jose conducted alpha testing of functionality and recommended changes and new functionality to the interface. The interface was validated using examples of immunization transformations being developed at that time by WHO specialists¹². After reaching the TRL7 level, the editor was demonstrated to FHIR experts - Vadim Peretokin, Oliver Egger and Brian Postlethwaite¹³ and received high praise from them. The development of the FML module took 2 person-months of analytical work, 4 person-months of programming and 2 person-months of verification and fine-tuning.

As a result of development, the module has reached TRL level 7 and is used by experts in everyday work as an auxiliary tool.

4.3. Visual TermX FML Editor

Figure 5 illustrates the simplest transformation in the visual editor. Nodes represent data objects, and edges represent transformations.

¹¹<https://matchbox.health>

¹²<https://worldhealthorganization.github.io/smart-immunizations>

¹³<https://www.linkedin.com/in/brianpos>

Figure 6: FML transformation with text functions.

Transformations are functions. Copy is the simplest function. This transformation visually depicts copying the attribute **a** from the **TLeft** model to the **b** attribute in the **TRight** model. The corresponding source code generated from this representation is presented in Listing 5 and transform source instance 2 to target instance 3.

The visual FML Editor implements the following patterns:

- Handling of structures and data types defined in FHIR StructureDefinition format (Figure 7).
- Capability to create subgroups. The ability to encapsulate rules within isolated space (Figure 8).
- Support for the FHIRPath language through the FML function “evaluate” (Figure 7, Listing 10).
- Manipulation of constants and functions (Figure 7).
- Integration of conditional “when” expressions, akin to “if” statements.
- Specialised support for complex data types (Figure 7) such as Coding, Quantity, Date, and Reference.
- String manipulation functions such as append and truncate (Figure 6).

Figure 6 showcases the graphical interface of the FML rule editor. It presents the characterisation of each interface according to the types of the subsets of the phenomena [25]. The left panel displays the models and functions utilised in the transformation process. In the central segment, models and functions are visualised alongside their attributes and

Figure 7: Transformation of Anamnesis model to FHIR observation.

interconnections. Selecting a model or function on the right side unveils its detailed structure, offering the option to define specific actions. When neither a model nor a function is selected, a list of available functions is presented in the right panel (Figure 8). The source instance *TLeft* and target instance *TRight* of the transformation in Figure 6 are given in Listing 7.

```

{
  "resourceType": "TLeft",
  "a": "123456789012"
  "b": "text"
}
->
{
  "resourceType": "TRight",
  "a": "1234567890",
  "b": "text/123456789012"
}

```

Listing 7: The source and target instances for FML transformation with string functions.

Figure 6 depicts the two actions: 1) copying attribute **TLeft.a** into attribute **TRight.a** with text truncation to 10 characters using the *truncate* transform function, and 2) concatenation of the attributes **TLeft.b**, **TLeft.a** and separator **"/** with transform function *append* and copying the output into attribute **TRight.b**. The right-click context menu displays meta-information about the transform function, including its type, parameters, associated models, and conditions. During data copying, the source and output attributes should have the same data type or be cast into the same data type. An entire object can be represented by the contextual variable **\$this**, which can be employed for copying or accessing model attributes.

```

{
  "resourceType": "Anamnesis",
  "patient": {
    "reference": "Patient/123",
  },
  "performed": "2023-08-10",
  "weight": "99.99"
}
->
{
  "resourceType": "Observation",
  "id": "b17e7be8-8b81-4bd8-a38c-5a052b01f3b2",
  "status": "final",
  "category": [{
    "coding": [{
      "system":
        "http://terminology.hl7.org/CodeSystem/observation-category",
      "code": "vital-signs"
    }]
  }],
  "code": {
    "coding": [{
      "system": "http://snomed.info/sct",
      "code": "27113001"
    }]
  },
  "subject": {
    "reference": "Patient/123"
  },
  "effectiveDateTime": "2023-08-10",
  "valueQuantity": {
    "value": 99.99,
    "unit": "kg",
    "system": "http://unitsofmeasure.org"
  }
}

```

Listing 8: The source and target instances for Anamnesis transformation.

Each model has a name and attributes. Each attribute has a name, data type and cardinality. Data types may be primitive, like string, integer or date, and complex, like `dateTime`, `Quantity`, or `CodeableConcept`. The complex data types may contain primitive datatypes or other complex types. For example, `Quantity` contains a decimal *value*, *unit* of type *string*, *system* of type *uri* and *code* of type *code*, or `CodeableConcept` contain an array of attributes with type *Coding*.

Figure 7 contains the transformation of the Anamnesis model to the FHIR `Observation` model. The source instance *Anamnesis* and target instance *Observation* of the transformation in Figure 7 are given in Listing 8. Anamnesis has attributes *patient* of type *Reference*, *performed* of type *dateTime* and *weight* of type *string*. They will be mapped to the *subject* of

Figure 8: The Anamnesis to Bundle FML transformation with subgroups.

type *Reference*, *effective* of type *dateTime* and *value* of type *Quantity* respectively. The mandatory fields *id*: *identifier*, *code*: *CodeableConcept*, *status*: *code*, *category*: *CodeableConcept* should be initialised in the FHIR Observation also. The attributes *patient* and *subject*, and *performed* and *effective* have the same data types and may be copied directly without any additional transformation. *weight* cannot be copied to *value* because of the different data types. The sub-object *Quantity* is created by pressing the icon “+” and linked to the attribute *value*. The string *weight* is cast to decimal and assigned to *Quantity.value*. The attributes *system* and *unit* are initialised as constants, and *code* are initialised through function *evaluate* and *FHIRPath* expression [15]. In this example, “constant” and “evaluate” transformers produce the same result. As a result, a sub-object of type *Quantity* will be created and omitted to the *value*. The constant *final* is used for *Observation status*. Each sub-object, function or even constant has at least one input and output parameter. Therefore, the constant is linked directly to the model through *\$this*, and not to the attributes. The function *uuid* generates a UUID-compatible identifier. The function *cc* generates the object of type *CodeableConcept* that may be used for *code* and *category* attributes. *cc* with parameters “http://snomed.info/sct”, “27113001” and “Body weight” that represents SNOMED code for body weight was used for *Observation.code*. The same result for the *category* was achieved by creating sub-objects *CodeableConcept* and *Coding* and assigning constants to them.

The first executable rule group have a single input and single output object according to the language rules. Additional subgroups may have

Figure 9: The graph of transformation Anamnesis model to FHIR observation.

multiple input and output parameters. If the transformation is intended to yield multiple output objects, they should be encapsulated within a more complex object. In FHIR, such an object is known as a **Bundle**[26].

Figure 8 presents the complex transformation of the source model **Anamnesis** to the target model **Bundle**. The logical model Anamnesis represents the list of measurements collected on admission to the hospital. Our simplified model contains weight and heart rate measurements. Further subgroups are established for each attribute within the source model, namely “Weight” discussed above and “HeartRate”. Within these subgroups, corresponding “Observation” models are generated and subsequently copied into the entry section of the “Bundle” (Figure 7).

4.4. The code generation algorithms

The description of the transformation process should result in an acyclic-directed graph from one or many source nodes to one or many output nodes in FHIR StructureMap format. Figure 9 represents the topological representation of Weight transformation from Figure 7. We will use Weight transformation to explain how the algorithm generates the FML syntax from a visual diagram.

The simplified algorithm for the generation of the FML syntax:

1. In creating a visual transformation diagram, an internal graph is formed, which is used by the algorithm. That graph significantly differs from the resulting graph. To ensure the accuracy of building the topology in the graph, the “Topology” button displays the sequence of graph traversal to the user. In Figure 7, the first 5 steps of the topology visualiser are highlighted with a pink background.
2. Find all root target objects. Our example transformation is Observation with alias **B**.
3. For each target object, find used attributes and create an isolated space for every attribute. In our example, the attributes used for object B are value, subject, effective, code, category, status, and ID. Two spaces were drawn in Figure 9 - S1 for *category* and S2 for *value*.
4. For each space, create two ordered arrays from the source (List A) and target (List B) elements. List A is composed by traversing from source elements in the direction of the target until encountering the first transformation function or direct copy operation, while List B is composed similarly by traversing from target elements in the direction of the source. For example, space S1 has List A=A, List B=B, B.1, B.1.1, space S2 has A=A, List B=B, B.2. Lists for space S1 are illustrated in Figure 10
5. With two lists and indices i and j that indicate positions in lists A and B, we can start traversing and composing rules. Before each iteration, both indices are incremented. If there’s no element at the index in the list for which this index is used, the index decreases to the previous value. This ensures we always have the source and target values while going through all levels. In our example for space S1, the source object remains A with each subsequent iteration. Simultaneously, with increased index j , the target object becomes the next object in list B (see Figure 11).
6. Each iteration to the next sub-level means creating a new rule in the StructureMap. Every rule requires source and target objects. As mentioned earlier, at each iteration, either a new element is selected, or the previous one is used. If a new element is selected, we must either choose a sub-element “ctx.element as var” or create a new

Figure 10: The lists for step 5.

Figure 11: The iteration of objects in the lists (step 6).

resource “create(’Resource’) as r1” to which values will be assigned later.

- Once the source and target objects have been created/selected, and we know which objects we are in the context of, we can specify all the rules that can be created within this context. There are 2 types of rules for direct copying and transform functions. For all connections between the source and target objects, the corresponding StructureMap *copy* rule is created. For the other transform functions, a recursive search is run for each target object attribute, and a chain of rules is created that leads to the creation or assignment of a value to that attribute. When the chain is found, a transform handler is selected for each rule within the chain and generated part appended to StructureMap.

The result of the transformation depicted in Figure 7 is presented in Listing 9 in FML notation. FML have very deep integration with FHIRPath. TermX FML Editor also supports the generation of transformations in FHIRPath notation. The algorithm for generating the FHIRPath syntax differs from the algorithm generating FML syntax and is

not a part of this paper. Listing 9 presents the alternative presentation of Figure 7 in FHIRPath notation.

```

group Weight(source src: Anamnesis, target tgt: Observation) {
  src -> tgt.id = uuid() as uuid575 "rule_674";
  src -> tgt.status = ('final') as constant576 "const_676";
  src -> tgt.category = create('CodeableConcept') as a then {
    src -> a.coding = create('Coding') as b then {
      src -> b.code = ('vital-signs') as constant605 "const_680";
      src -> b.system =
        ('http://terminology.hl7.org/CodeSystem/observation-category')
          as constant626 "const_681";
    } "rule_679";
  } "rule_678";
  src -> tgt.code =
    cc('http://snomed.info/sct', '27113001', 'Body weight')
    as cc578 "rule_683";
  src.patient as a -> tgt.subject = a "dset_685";
  src.performed as a -> tgt.effective = a "dset_687";
  src -> tgt.value = create('Quantity') as a then {
    src -> a.unit = ('kg') as constant584 "const_690";
    src -> a.system = ('http://unitsofmeasure.org')
      as constant586 "const_691";
    src.weight as b -> a.code = evaluate(b, kg)
      as evaluate633 "rule_692";
    src.weight as c -> a.value = cast(c, 'decimal')
      as cast664 "rule_693";
  } "rule_689";
}

```

Listing 9: The result of visual transformation to the source code in FML notation

```

group Weight(source src: Anamnesis, target tgt: Observation) {
  src -> uuid() as uuid575, tgt.id = uuid575 "rule_717";
  src -> ('final') as constant576,
    tgt.status = constant576 "rule_718";
  src -> tgt.category = create('CodeableConcept') as a,
    a.coding = create('Coding') as b,
    ('http://terminology.hl7.org/CodeSystem/observation-category')
      as c626,
    ('vital-signs') as constant605, b.code = constant605,
    b.system = c626 "rule_719";
  src -> cc('http://snomed.info/sct', '27113001', 'Body weight')
    as cc578, tgt.code = cc578 "rule_720";
  src -> (%src.patient) as a, tgt.subject = a "rule_721";
  src -> (%src.performed) as a, tgt.effective = a "rule_722";
  src -> tgt.value = create('Quantity') as a, (%src.weight) as b,
    cast(b, 'decimal') as cast664, evaluate(b, kg) as evaluate633,
    ('http://unitsofmeasure.org') as constant586,
    ('kg') as constant584, a.unit = constant584,
    a.system = constant586, a.code = evaluate633,
    a.value = cast664 "rule_723";
}

```

Listing 10: The result of visual transformation to the source code in FHIRPath notation

4.5. Compatibility with FHIR StructureMap resource

Visual TermX FML Editor creates transformations following the FHIR StructureMap specification. At the same time, the visual editor has additional data - about the objects and sub-objects used in the transformation, their position on the diagram, colour, expand/collapse features, etc. The SVG picture is also generated when saving the transformation description in the visual editor. The SVG picture lets you get a visual overview of the transformation without using the editor. Additional information required for the visual editor and SVG picture are saved as *fml-export* and *fml-svg* extensions of the FHIR StructureMap resource 11.

```
{
  "resourceType": "StructureMap",
  ...
  "extension": [{
    "url": "fml-export",
    "valueString":
      {
        "groups":
          {
            "main":
              {
                "objects":
                  {
                    "TLeft":
                      {
                        "expanded": false,
                        ...
                      }
                    }
                }
              }
            }
          }
        }
      },
    {
      "url": "fml-svg",
      "valueString": "data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf-8,%3Csvg"
      ...
    }
  ]
}
```

Listing 11: The TermX extensions of the StructureMap resource.

4.6. Assessment

The designed FML Editor was successfully tested with TalTech and TEHIK analysts. We divided the assessment into two sessions. Each session consisted of theoretical and practical parts, each lasting one hour. In the first session, basic theoretical knowledge about FML and the principles of operation of the FML Editor were given. The practical part of the first session assessed the analyst's ability to create a transformation from a simple logical model (up to 10 attributes) into a single FHIR resource. The complexity of the task can be equated to the Weight transformation in

Figure 7. 9 out of 9 participants completed the task within the allotted hour.

In the second session, more complex structures were considered - working with groups and importing external transformations. The practical part of the second session assessed the analyst's ability to create a transformation that creates a Bundle of resources from at least two resources. The task's difficulty can be equated to the Bundle transformation in Figure 8. 6 out of 8 participants completed the task partially within the allotted hour. All participants confirmed that the process of creating a transformation was clear and that they would be able to complete the task later on their own.

Finally, we assessed the clarity of the textual and visual transformations created by analysts who participated in the training and analysts who did not participate in the training. The 5% of analysts were able to answer what textual transformation did, and 100% described the business logic behind visual transformation.

5. Discussion

We discovered that mapping languages are utilized for defining mappings and transformations between different data structures. The QVT framework is commonly employed in model-driven development and for handling model transformation tasks. FML is the only mapping language that implements the QVT specification and is supported by HL7 in the healthcare domain.

The FML language syntax and tools are quite complex, and at the moment, there are no visual editors for working with FML. As a result, FML is not widely used. We developed a visual TermX FML Editor that utilised FML as the transformation language, relied on HAPI FHIR as the foundation for the transformation engine, and transformed data from input sources into output sources. By leveraging FHIRPath functionality, we managed to navigate various constraints imposed by the FML specification and the HAPI FHIR implementation. We implemented all the transform functions supported by HAPI FHIR. The existing list of functions in the FML Editor can be easily extended as needed by any implementer. We developed a visual TermX FML Editor for creating transformations by business analysts. The visual editor hides the complexity of the FML language and is likely to gain wider adoption.

The results of our assessment were very good. They show that the visual FML Editor can solve the problem of developing the transformations

after very short training. The transformations in Figures 7 and 8 show real-life problems arising from the need to support several interoperability standards simultaneously mentioned in the introduction. The fact that the transformation is created only by a business analyst without the need for a programmer shows that the visual TermX FML Editor we developed changes the approach to developing transformations and allows the business analyst to do the programmer's work.

The TermX FML Editor is designed as a unidirectional solution that generates FHIR StructureMap from visual representation. The FML Editor allows you to visualise the source code of StructureMap in a limited number of use cases, such as the *copy* transform function. During the research, we decided to forego bidirectional support for FML, meaning the import of arbitrary language constructs into the visual FML Editor. This decision was made due to the complexity of supporting many ways to express the same language construct. This limitation is justified because our primary goal was to create a tool for business analysts rather than developers.

At this point, the editor does not prevent all potential problems. For example, a user can assign two values to one target element. This situation in the Pascal and SQL languages may be expressed with the syntax: *variableA:=value1; variableA:=value2;*. Like in the other languages in the FML, the latest rule will override the value of the target variable. Another example is about datatype conversions. The visual editor does not warn the user about non-matching datatypes. Issues with data type may be caught during runtime execution of the transformation in a sandbox. More checks will be added to the editor to prevent errors.

Visual TermX FML Editor was created primarily as an editor for transformations. As a result of the development, a syntax was created for storing information about objects, elements, their location on the screen, etc. To some extent, the visual syntax of TermX and the generation of FML code can be correlated with the visual language Query by Example (QBE) and the generation of SQL code [27]. Like a visual editor, QBE provides a graphical interface in which a graphical representation of a data manipulation or data description statement can be constructed.

In future works, we plan to describe the formalism used by the visual editor, describe the formalism for the FML language, and create a map for bidirectional transformation [28]. Later, the visual editor could become more language-agnostic and support other model-transformation languages of the QVT framework [12].

6. Conclusion

Through this research, we have successfully developed a visual TermX FML Editor that hides the FML language’s complexity.

We evaluate the usability of visual FML Editor for transforming informational models into FHIR resources. The results demonstrated that business analysts could effectively describe transformations after just one hour of training. The visual presentation of the transformation is clear even for analysts without previous FML knowledge.

Code availability

The editor has been published as an independent library on GitLab[29] and integrated into the TermX suite[23]. For the development of the FML editor, we utilised the open-source project Drawflow[30].

Authors’ contribution

I.B. designed the idea and wrote the manuscript with support from G.P. All authors contributed to the final version. G.P., R.B., Jose Costa Teixeira and P.R. supervised the project.

I.B. and R.B. designed the solution and architecture of TermX FML Editor, which R.B. developed with the support of Daniel Dubrovski. Jose Costa Teixeira conducted an alpha testing of the FML editor.

6.1. Conflict of Interest

No conflicts of interest are declared.

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